

TEACHING READING USING PRE-READING TASKS

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Annotatsiya: Mazkur maqolada o'quvchilarda o'qish darslarini samarali tashkillashda muhim bo'lgan jihatlar namunalar asosida yoritilgan. Shuningdek, o'qish darslarida o'quvchilarining nutq salohiyatini rivojlantirishda qo'llanuvchi metodlar va asosiy talablar aks ettirilgan, hamda o'qishni o'rgatishni bir qancha tamoillari keltirilgan. O'qish darslari orqali bolalarning fikrlash usullarini yuksaltirish haqida ma'lumotlar berilgan.

Kalit so'zlar: aqliy o'qish, mahorat, o'qish usullari, so'zlarni aniqlash va tushunish, ravon o'qish qobiliyatlari, g'oyalarni bog'lash, tasavvur, lug'at o'qishning asosiy omilidir.

Abstract: In this article, the aspects that are important in the effective organization of reading lessons for students are covered based on examples. Also, the methods and basic requirements used in the development of students' speech potential in the reading lessons are reflected, as well as several principles of teaching reading are presented. Information is given about improving the ways of thinking of children through the reading lessons.

Keywords: Mental reading, skill, reading methods, definition and understanding of words, fluent reading skills, connecting ideas, imagination, prediction is a major factor in reading.

Reading is about understanding written texts. It is a complex activity that involves both perception and thought. Reading consists of two related processes: word recognition and comprehension. Word recognition refers to the process of perceiving how written symbols correspond to one's spoken language. Comprehension is the process of making sense of words, sentences and connected text. Readers typically make use of background knowledge, vocabulary, grammatical knowledge, experience with text and other strategies to help them understand written text.

Reading skills are the cognitive processes that a reader uses in making sense of a text. For fluent readers, most of the reading skills are employed unconsciously and

automatically. When confronted with a challenging text, fluent readers apply these skills consciously and strategically in order to comprehend.

There are numerous reading skills that learners need to master to become proficient readers: extracting main ideas, reading for specific information, understanding text organization, predicting, checking comprehension, inferring, dealing with unfamiliar words, linking ideas, understanding complex sentences, understanding writer's style and writing summaries. But if adult learners are psychologically prepared for reading and the matter is only in acquiring basic reading skills, enriching vocabulary stock and mastering at least few grammar rules, then the situation with young elementary readers is quite different.

Learners read effectively only when they are ready. The reader's preparedness to read is called 'reading readiness'. According to Thorndike's law of learning, the first requisite for beginning reading is an interest in reading. Reading stories, allowing learners to draw and read charts, displaying readable messages, providing picture books and labeling the objects will stimulate their interests.

At any level, the following skills are necessary for a language learners to become a proficient reader:

- automatic, rapid letter recognition
- automatic, rapid word recognition
- the ability to use context as an aid to comprehension

While teaching reading the following approaches should not be neglected:

Focus on one skill at a time. Explain the purpose of working on this skill, and convince the learners of its importance in reading effectively. Work on an example of using the skill with the whole class. Explain your thinking aloud as you do the exercise. Assign learners to work in pairs on an exercise where they practice using the same skill. Require them to explain their thinking to each other as they work. Discuss learners' answers with the whole class. Ask them to explain how they got their answers. Encourage polite disagreement, and require explanations of any differences in their answers. Reading becomes effective when teacher starts with words that are familiar to learners, uses simple structures, blackboard and flashcards, and gives emphasis to recognizing and understanding the meaning of a word simultaneously. As far as young learners are concerned teaching reading should be started when a learner can learn his/her own mother-tongue. Also, it is suggested to use some kind of reading repetition or practice and progress monitoring. Moreover, teachers should always keep in mind the various problems of reading a foreign language.

It is useful to know if a learner can read nonsense words such as '*flep, tridding and pertollic*' as the ability to read nonsense words depends on rapid and accurate

association of sounds with symbols. Good readers do this easily so they can decipher new words and attend to the meaning of the passage. Poor readers usually are slower and make more mistakes in sounding out words. Their comprehension suffers as a consequence. Poor readers improve if they are taught in an organized, systematic manner how to decipher the spelling code and sound words out.

There are also several principles behind the teaching of reading:

Principle 1: Reading is not a passive skill. Reading is an incredibly active occupation. To do it successfully, we have to understand what the words mean, see the pictures the words are painting, understand the arguments, and work out if we agree with them.

Principle 2: learners need to be engaged with what they are reading. As with everything else in lessons, pupils who are not engaged with the reading text - not actively interested in what they are doing - are less likely to benefit from it. When they are really fired up by the topic or the task, they get much more from what is in front of them.

Principle 3: learners should be encouraged to respond to the content of a reading text not just to the language. Of course, it is important to study reading texts for the way they use language, the number of paragraphs they contain and how many times they use relative clauses. But the meaning, the message of the text, is just as important and we must give pupils a chance to respond to that message in some way.

Principle 4: Prediction is a major factor in reading. When we read texts in our own language, we frequently have a good idea of the content before we actually read. Book covers give us a hint of what's in the book, photographs and headlines hint at what articles are about and reports look like reports before we read a single word. The moment we get this hint - the book cover, the headline, the word-processed page - our brain starts predicting what we are going to read. Expectations are set up and the active process of reading is ready to begin. Teachers should give learners 'hints' so that they can predict what's coming too. It will make them better and more engaged readers.

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